

27th March 2025 - Nice, France

Collaboration on international ICT standardisation

Joint roadmaps development

1. About INSTAR

INSTAR is an EU-funded Coordination and Support Action (CSA) promoting the implementation of Europe's Digital Partnerships and bilateral agreements, collaborating with like-minded entities in Australia, Canada, Japan, Singapore, South Korea, Taiwan, and the USA. In this regard, INSTAR aims to cultivate a unified vision and develop strategic roadmaps for ICT standards in domains such as Artificial Intelligence (AI); Cybersecurity and Digital Identification (eID); Data; Cloud, Edge, IoT and Internet; 5G+ 6G; and Quantum technologies, as critical enablers of future innovation. INSTAR unites experts, policymakers, and industry leaders to ensure global standards align with market needs and do not hinder technology innovation. By harmonising objectives and strengthening Europe's leadership in ICT standardisation, INSTAR contributes to more secure, competitive, and widely adopted digital technologies.

Over 30 months, INSTAR will:

- Establish targeted Task Forces with European and International standardisation experts, to identify their respective priorities and promote commonalities.
- Produce joint standardisation roadmaps across the aforementioned technology areas, contributing to the development of harmonized standards.
- Develop the INSTAR Dashboard which will include among others:
 - A standards tracer to systematically gather, update and analyse information from SDOs and relevant web portals. This tool will provide AI-powered services to analyse the collected data and generate new knowledge.
 - A content library with training resources and learning materials for standards developed by INSTAR's academic partners.
 - A detailed mapping of knowledge areas against Standards Development Organisations (SDOs) and the INSTAR international partners

1 Introduction

INSTAR and the Telecommunications Technology Association (TTA) of the Republic of Korea signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) in September 2024. One of the MoU's objectives was to discuss and agree on a joint roadmap, which shall list commonly agreed priorities in the six technological areas covered by INSTAR and the MoU.

Through the reciprocal exchange of materials, strong alignment was initially observed in Cybersecurity, Data, and Cloud, Edge, IoT. In this context, a physical workshop was held in Nice, France to identify specific topics of mutual interest in these domains, for INSTAR and the TTA to jointly support in international Standards Development Organisations (IDSOs).

This event brought together the INSTAR consortium and European Task Force experts, as well as members of the TTA, European Commission and ETSI, facilitating strategic alignment between the stakeholders.

The workshop played a catalyst role in:

- Showcasing the INSTAR and TTA standardisation roadmaps for Cybersecurity, Data, and Cloud, Edge, IoT.
- Preliminarily identifying and mapping common standardisation priorities from both sides.
- Conceptualising the structure of the joint roadmaps and their intended use.
- Kickstarting the conversation for cooperation on 6G and quantum technologies.
- Developing a concrete timeline of immediate next steps and long-term actions.

2. Outcomes and next steps

The agreed timeline shared across all technology areas (Table 1) foresees the publishing of the INSTAR-TTA joint roadmaps by December 2025.

Table 1. Timeline for the INSTAR-TTA joint roadmaps

Timeline	Milestone	Description
March 2025	1 Workshop TTA-INSTAR	Exchange and discuss common topics on CEI, Cybersecurity, and Data, as identified through roadmap exchanges between INSTAR and TTA
April 2025	Designation of Experts and appointment of convenors	A Convenor for each technical area should be selected Each party selects experts to participate in the email discussions The selected experts should be reported to the Convenors
April - June 2025	Expert Discussion (via email)	Convenors initiate and facilitate dedicated email discussions Discussion about priorities to be included in the joint roadmap across all technology areas
July 2025	Checkpoint & Preparation for the 2nd Workshop	Check progress of each area and start a preparation for 2nd Workshop
October 2025	Finalization of Expert Discussions	Consolidate all discussions into finalized joint roadmaps Prepare presentation for the 2nd Workshop
November 2025	2 Workshop TTA-INSTAR	Exchange and discuss common topics on AI and other areas Approve the finalized joint roadmaps and establish promotion strategies Identify potential collaborative initiatives for further cooperation
December 2025	Publication & Promotion of Joint Roadmaps	Publish e-deliverables and promote them within respective regions Share roadmaps with standardization bodies and relevant stakeholder

Leading up to the joint roadmaps, the following concrete actions were identified for each of the areas addressed in the workshop:

2.1 Cybersecurity

- Present the INSTAR-TTA MoU and TTA's workshop slides to key SDO working groups, such as TC SAI, TC CYBER, TC ESI

Scott Cadzow, INSTAR Cybersecurity ETF member | April / May 2025

- Connect each of these bodies with the relevant TTA working groups, to promote an exchange of their work programme, highlight any publications, and share their meeting calendars.

Scott Cadzow, INSTAR Cybersecurity ETF member | April / May 2025

- Prepare a liaison request to and from SC27/WG4 projects on Data provenance and Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS).

Jan deMeer, INSTAR Cybersecurity ETF member | April / May 2025

- Meet with multiple working groups and technical committees within the remit of the TTA conference in Seoul, Republic of Korea (3rd- 5th November 2025). Target entities include Taiwan, Japan and Singapore.

INSTAR Cybersecurity ETF lead | June 2025

- Intensify efforts to synchronise the work of European and international SDOs and the INSTAR-TTA conversations.

Technical members of the INSTAR Cybersecurity ETF and TTA | June 2025

- Pursue synergies with similar European and Korean initiatives.

INSTAR consortium, TTA | Ongoing efforts April -Nov 2025

2.2 Cloud, Edge, IoT, Internet (CEI)

- Identify 20 relevant work items across European and international SDOs, particularly ISO/IEC, ITU-T and oneM2M.

INSTAR CEI ETF, TTA | June 2025

- Prioritise the top 5 listed work items in order of relevance, impact and urgency.

INSTAR CEI ETF, TTA | July 2025

- Allocate resources: identify specific experts to work on promoting each of the work items.

INSTAR CEI ETF lead, TTA | September/October 2025

- Convene to discuss implementation based on the joint roadmaps.

INSTAR CEI ETF lead, TTA | November 2025

2.3 Data

- Align priorities in ISO TC JTC1 ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 Internet of things and digital twin

INSTAR Data ETF lead (Antonio Kung), TTA (Minah) | April 2025

- Align priorities in ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 32 Data management and interchange

INSTAR Data ETF lead (Antonio Kung), TTA (Minah) | April 2025

- Align priorities in the forthcoming kick-off of the new ETSI TC Data.

INSTAR Data ETF lead and Scott Cadzow, TTA via SeungMyeong Jeong from KETI | April 2025

- Explore opportunities for collaboration in CEN/CENELEC JTC 25 Data management, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge.

INSTAR Data ETF lead, TTA | April 2025

- Consider Smart Applications REFerence Ontology (SAREF) by ETSI in future standardisation efforts related to interoperability

INSTAR Data ETF lead, TTA | Continuous

2.3 5G+/6G

- Further explore common knowledge areas and priority topics, such as architectures, energy efficiency in terms of networking and AI for 6G resource management.

INSTAR 5G+/6G ETF lead, TTA | April 2025

- Propose a follow-up technical meeting with ETF experts on sub-topics and standardisation aspects (e.g. 3GPP release 20/21). *INSTAR 5G+/6G ETF lead, TTA | May 2025*

INSTAR 5G+/6G ETF lead | April 2025

- Deliver joint workshop on standardisation in 6G.

INSTAR 5G+/6G ETF lead | May 2025

- Promote the EU-Korean common vision to relevant international conferences (e.g. IEEE).

INSTAR 5G+/6G ETF, TTA | June, Nov 2025

- Address the possibility of joint calls under SNS JU after the Digital Partnership Council meeting 2025.

INSTAR 5G+/6G ETF lead | June 2025

2.4 Quantum

- Map existing pilot projects in the EU and Korean national quantum networks, such as EuroQCI, that can address shared standardisation gaps and test interoperability solutions in real-world environments.

INSTAR Quantum ETF lead, TTA | July 2025

- Map South Korean and EU standardisation priorities, particularly in areas such as, quantum communication (QKD, hybrid PQC), trust models, interoperability, satellite-terrestrial integration.

INSTAR Quantum ETF, TTA | July, Nov 2025

- Strengthen EU-South Korea collaboration within ISO/IEC JTC 3, particularly through joint proposals and technical contributions to the Ad Hoc Group on Quantum Communications (led by South Korea, building on aligned priorities in areas such as QKD, PQC integration, and interoperability).

INSTAR Quantum ETF, TTA | Nov 2025

3. Conclusion

The joint workshop between INSTAR and the TTA was a catalyst in the strategic alignment of the EU and Republic of Korea for ICT standardisation, leading to the identification of mutual interests in several key technological areas, including Cybersecurity, Data and Cloud, Edge, IoT.

The workshop outcomes highlight the importance of harmonising objectives and strengthening Europe's leadership in ICT standardisation. The next steps involve publishing joint roadmaps by December 2025, which will guide collaborative efforts in the identified technological areas. For this, a detailed timeline is provided (see Table 1 above).

These joint roadmaps will serve as a blueprint for future INSTAR International Task Forces, promoting commonalities and synergies between European and international standardisation bodies. The concrete actions outlined for each technology area, focusing mainly on promoting relevant work items across relevant committees, SDOs, and international conferences, demonstrate a clear path forward, with specific tasks and timelines to achieve the set goals.

Overall, the INSTAR-TTA cooperation is essential for addressing shared standardisation gaps and ensuring interoperability in real-world environments across countries. The successful implementation of these joint roadmaps will enhance Europe's leadership in ICT standardization and promote global technological advancement.

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Joint roadmaps development

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27 March 2025, 09:00 - 17:30 CET

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